

Co-Creating Circular
Resource Flows in Cities

constRuctive mEtabolic processes For materiaL fLOWs in
urban and peri-urban environments across Europe

Deliverable 5.5

Citizen Engagement and Capacity Building

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Introduction

About REFLOW

REFLOW is an EU Horizon 2020 research project running from 2019-2022, which aims to enable the transition of European cities towards circular and regenerative practices. More specifically, REFLOW uses Fab Labs and makerspaces as catalysers of a systemic change in urban and peri-urban environments, which enable, visualize and regulate “four freedoms”: free movement of materials, people, (technological) knowledge and commons, in order to reduce materials consumption, maximize multifunctional use of (public) spaces and envisage regenerative practices. The project will provide best practices aligning market and government needs in order to create favorable conditions for the public and private sector to adopt circular economy (CE) practices. REFLOW is creating new CE business models within six pilot cities: Amsterdam, Berlin, Cluj-Napoca, Milan, Paris and Vejle and assess their social, environmental and economic impact, by enabling active citizen involvement and systemic change to re-think the current approach to material flows in cities.

REFLOW Vision

A circular and regenerative city in REFLOW represents an urban system with social and business practices which place equal attention to **social, environmental and economic impact**; where **technology** is open and represents a central enabler of positive social and environmental change; where the urban system ensures and support resilience of social and ecological systems; where **governance** is collaborative and inclusive; where **knowledge** is shared, and **stakeholders** are active and involved.

About the deliverable

This deliverable describes the Citizen Engagement Strategy and Deployment Plan for each pilot city (governance, purpose, key actors and roles, segments and target groups and communication), and suggests principles and models for “circular citizens” initiatives (to be addressed to other EU cities). For all the city pilots, engaging citizens in the transition towards a circular economy is fundamental, and to understand the complexity of the challenge faced in their specific urban environments, they need to comprehend the dynamics and perspectives of all the stakeholders involved. In a traditional linear economy, consisting of a model shaped in: design, manufacture, purchase, consume and dispose, citizens are involved in the last three phases. In an alternative circular economy model, where we: design for recyclability, manufacture with recycled resources, purchase and consume consciously, and dispose for collection and recycling, citizens play a key role. Their participation is required for this transition to happen, and the value arising from their participation has to be acknowledged. The aim of this deliverable is to understand how we can enable circulation of this renewed value in resources for all the stakeholders involved.

Structure of the report

The structure of the report follows chronologically the activities undertaken, especially, during the last year of the piloting activities in regards to citizen engagement. The first chapter reports the citizen engagement strategies implemented by the 6 pilot cities, resulting from the bilateral interviews, an on-line workshop and a survey. The second chapter gives a definition of the importance of citizen engagement in the circular economy, and tries to inspire readers by giving examples of different ways to empower citizens and engage them in the decision-making process. In the last chapter, six recommendations derived from the pilot experiences are drawn. The same are also added in the appendix, *Circular Citizens Handbook*, with the aim to inspire other European municipalities, policy makers and urban practitioners that desire to move towards a more inclusive urban circular metabolism.

1 Mapping and analysis of the citizen involvement strategies implemented by the 6 Reflow partner cities

This report aimed to inspect the role of citizens in circular economy solutions by investigating and analyzing the citizen engagement strategy and deployment plan in the six Reflow partner cities: Amsterdam, Berlin, Cluj-Napoca, Milan, Paris, and Vejle. Reflow started in June 2019, and despite the challenges brought by Covid-19 since the beginning of 2020, especially in terms of limiting public events and citizen participation, the six pilot cities have conducted local activities and co-design workshops, and prototyped circular solutions involving local key stakeholders and the civil society.

Table 1 illustrates how the task T.5.5 was carried out and, furthermore, the different methods that were employed to collect the data. In the following sub-chapters, the different phases will be addressed. These include, Informal interviews, an online workshop, and a survey.

Table 1. Methods diagram

	Mar '21	Apr '21	May '21	Jun '21	Jul '21	Aug '21	Sep '21	Oct '21	Nov '21	Dec '21	Jan '22	Feb '22	Mar '22	Apr '22	May '22
Informal interviews with pilot cities															
Online workshop with pilot cities															
Case study and best practices research															
On-line survey to															

pilot cities															
One-to-one interviews with pilot cities representatives															
Draft D5.5															
Final D5.5															

1.1 Informal interviews

Between March and April 2021 online interviews were conducted with the partners from the city pilots in order to identify the progress of local activities and the methods employed for engaging with local stakeholders and citizens so far since the beginning of the project. To the partners, together with the invitation to the semi-structured interview, it was also sent a draft of questions that would be asked. *Table 2* displays the interview’s protocol.

Table 2. Interview’s protocol

1	Could you give us a brief description of the pilot case scenario?
2	Which are your main motivations to engage with citizens in the pilot case?
3	Instead, in your point of view, which are the motivations of citizens to participate?
4	What was the participatory strategy that the pilot partners initially developed, and who were the key actors?
5	Were you guided by certain good practices in particular? If so, could you mention a few?
6	What participatory methods, tools or platforms were in place?
7	Then COVID-19 came, what impact did it have on the initial participatory strategy? What changes were you forced to make?
8	Do you feel like something is missing due to limited resources or capacity? or do you think of any other barriers that you have encountered?

The interviews, after the agreement of the interviewees, were recorded for internal use. The six interviews lasted around 45 - 60 minutes. Below results will be summarized and the key points, derived from each of the interviews with the 6 pilot city partners, will be highlighted.

1.1.1 Berlin - Waste Heat

Berlin city partners changed since the beginning of the project. Initially the municipal partner involved was another one with respect to the Berlin Water Management entity (IWA), which is now a partner of the local consortium. This has implied the overall change of the pilot case and the technology.

The focus of the Berlin pilot is on particular energy management, the wastewater heat. That means heat sourced from water that would otherwise be wasted and not recovered. This technology is still a niche in the environmental technology world, and it is part of making heating more sustainable. One of the main outcomes of the pilot will be a web application. The web application matches potential heat generated from wastewater (supply side) with heat demands from surrounding buildings (demand side). Users can search specific locations and additionally insert their actual heat demand data for that location. Even though it is a not fully explored material flow, wastewater heat has a circular aspect too. In order to better communicate such a rather abstract and very technical solution the city partners have released a series of short [clips](#). Through this choice it was possible to reach the target audience, such as the public and private real estate developers, but also citizens in order to introduce them to this solution.

Figure 1. Berlin city pilot © REFLOW

The first clip, for instance, is explaining the very fundamental mechanics behind recovering wastewater heating by using the application that the technical partners are developing within the Reflow project. Basically, technicians are developing software which localizes sources of wastewater with consumers. This means, the software creates a matchmaking for circular heating and links buildings or properties that could use this innovative solution on a broader scale.

From the citizen engagement perspective it is not an easy case. In this regard, pilot city partners were in contact with [CityLAB Berlin](#), a public experimental laboratory for the city of the future. In this environment representatives from government, civil society, academia and start-ups collaboratively develop new ideas for how to both ensure and enhance the livability of Berlin as a city. The CityLAB combines elements of a digital workshop, a co-working space and event space into a single location where participation and innovation are jointly pursued. Usually, there are showcased all kinds of projects that are relevant for the city, the society and that require a certain degree of research and scientific knowledge. Therefore, the idea is that in this space could be exhibited a physical model of a district (1:20), with a large touchscreen in which users can insert an address to see if there is a potential wastewater heat source. Hence, if someone comes to the CityLAB, and usually they do have recurring visitors (e.g. universities), they could see the wastewater heat model physically. Additionally, CityLab runs workshops, so developers and researchers could gather more information and see how the technology works. Unfortunately, the waste water heat model, due to COVID-19, was not implemented, and people were reached digitally, with direct contact and through videos. Pilot’s aim is to raise awareness on such a technical and rather new solution, and a certain sense of accountability.

Since the beginning, pilot city partners have identified a matrix of stakeholders to be targeted, such as private developers, that could then apply this technology, either on new buildings but also to the refurbished one. In addition to them, also public developers, housing associations, cooperatives and semi-public companies were contacted.

1.1.2 Paris - Fair Tracker

Paris pilot city focuses its research on wood of temporary construction, which includes events, co-working in temporary occupation spaces but also in the movie industry. Pilots’ activities are centered among three different access to the resource: “tools”, “incubation”, and “formation and awareness”.

The first, ‘tool’, focuses on how to create and design with reuse materials. The aim is to create a device that tracks the material and creates a database for designers and entrepreneurs. Fundamental would be the availability of a *smart storage system*, which monitors and quantifies exactly what is available at any specific circumstance. Secondly, “incubation” refers to the collection of ideas and the development of strategies in relation to the circularity of the material. In this regard, *Volumes has created* an incubation program supporting startups working in the construction sector. Lastly, “formation and awareness”, is about how to reach citizens, local stakeholders but also big companies. Accordingly, the aim is to create a label which will permit whoever is interested to understand how the object has been made, screening the different components, and where they came from. Through this it would be possible to decrypt the intrinsic circular value. In addition, the pilot organized training programs, such as “Circular Making” and, interestingly, was specifically targeting unemployed people.

Due to the technicality of the material flow object of the pilot solution, Paris city partners, especially in regards to the tools and the incubation programs, targeted mainly designers, professionals and craftsmen. Whereas, citizens would

partially be the focus of the label development. However, the label process is the overarching solution: it values the efforts of professionals, designers and craftsmen in the reuse of wood, and it helps in raising awareness among citizens.

Figure 2. Paris city pilot © REFLOW

As previously mentioned, Paris city partners mainly targeted designers, craftsmen or architects. The reason why citizens and the civil society was not engaged since the beginning was due to the approach of the design thinking methods. This method, according to city partners, required a basic knowledge and some previous experiences.

Initially pilot city partners attended public events to promote the project and the different solutions. When the pandemic hit all the activities turned online. However, according to city partners, the impacts of the circularity in the wood stream are less tangible than textile, food or plastic, therefore the engagement of citizens is also more challenging. This is due to the fact that citizens are not commonly in contact with waste wood in their daily life.

Interestingly, by attending different public events the project got attention and city partners started receiving emails about people dismantling and needing to get rid of things. However, one of the main obstacles in the pilot solution is the logistics of a good storage. This means to have a good inventory of what is there and to know exactly how to use it. Paris would like to work on the “*inverted design algorithm*”, and design in accordance with what is in the storage. Pilot city partners see the potential of empowering citizens on certain tasks, especially for covering the lack of human resources by training unemployed, or not qualified, people and engaging them in the circular solution.

1.1.3 Cluj-Napoca - PLEnergy

Cluj-Napoca city pilot focuses on energy efficiencies in different scenarios: citizens engagement and awareness raising, policy making on energy efficiency and circular economy and designing and implementing solutions for energy efficiency.

Initially, city partners conducted a stakeholder mapping, through which all the stakeholders that could be engaged and interested in the project were identified and, subsequently, consulted in roundtables. Additionally, public meetings at the Civic Imagination and Innovation Center (CIIC) were organized. The center is a place where local government representatives, citizens and specialists from economic and academic fields meet and discuss the challenges and necessary urban transformations of the city. It is a communication, research and promotion tool, as well as an open place for debates at the disposal of experts from different fields and any citizen willing to participate. The center coordinates and guides complex networks of participatory governance, including academia, NGOs, trade unions and professional associations. During the meetings the importance of energy efficiency and circular economy implemented in the city development strategy was presented. Furthermore, partners carried out webinars and presentations in public schools and universities.

One of the pilot solutions is SISTAM (Energy Tree), a public utility installation that would be implemented in urban areas, and would produce energy, collect data on environmental indicators and also interact with people by answering their questions on energy production, pollution and other environmental factors. SISTAM would be strictly interconnected between technology and awareness. However, only the prototyping phase is explored in the framework of REFLOW.

Remarkably, citizens in Cluj-Napoca are very concerned about their city environment and sustainability, but most strikingly are already aware of topics like energy efficiency. At present there is a certain enthusiasm in the civic society (entrepreneurs, organizations, NGOs, ...) and the Municipality is a catalyst of the situation and this has helped a lot to this devotion. The municipality of Cluj-Napoca has promoted citizens' engagement and participatory processes, like the participatory budget. Additionally, the implementation of the CIIC, with recurring meetings and debates in different fields and policy spheres, spurred participation in the city. Lastly, there is, also, an application named “City App” in which anyone can report any type of issues in the city to which the Municipality will then intervene. Importantly, also, the whole local ecosystem, composed of universities, The Municipality, entrepreneurs and other companies have been, efficiently, working together for years.

Figure 3. Cluj-Napoca city pilot © REFLOW

In relation to one pilot solutions, it consists in the retrofit of a university dormitory - a building owned by the Municipality - with a simple retrofitting kit, that could also be applied to any other buildings. This retrofitting kit just consists of a simple behavioral guidebook and new lighting, sockets and other electric connections with the addition of the installment of a smart mirroring system. Importantly, the tenants of this pilot building are the students from the technical school. Therefore, this would also be a case study for them - *put learning into practice*. At the time of the informal interview, Covid-19 didn't really delay pilot activities. City partners just turned everything online and postponed site visits with students and experts. City partners targeted, mainly, public entities, while the private sector would not be directly engaged.

1.1.4 Milan - Food Market 4.0

According to the partners from the pilot city of Milan, they initially wanted to focus their activities on the material flows and the technologies related to the urban food system, having the city covered markets at the center, and therefore as mentioned “*focusing on a micro dimension*”. In fact, an initial selection of public markets, which could work on sustainability and circularity practices, was identified.

This proposal was reviewed due to the arrival of the pandemic and the adoption of the safety measures, and above all because covered municipal markets were already “circular enough”. This means that given the small entity of flows managed, traders were careful to minimize waste, mainly for wisdom and economic savings. While, in regards to safety restrictions, public markets were still welcoming people for trading activities, therefore, the application of innovative prototypes and new technical solutions, understandably, was not a priority of the market vendors. Accordingly, the pilot's

partners adapted the initial strategy. Higher-level local stakeholders were identified, such as SO.GE.M.I. (the Municipal Company for the Installation and Operation of Wholesale Food Markets in Milan), Amsa (the Municipal Company managing the waste collection in Milan), and the Milan Food Policy (a set of policies by which the Municipality has outlined a shared vision on the future relationship of the city with food and defined the key actions to implement this vision, harmonizing the various projects on the subject of food).

Through this new strategy, the city pilot’s aim was to aggregate the flows of the city through a macro-approach (by involving more strategic stakeholders) and to identify their potential for a circular economy model at city-region level. However, simultaneously, with the help of the FabLab, the aim was also to engage with the market vendors and other local stakeholders active in the circular economy sphere (start-ups and associations). City pilot’s goal is to apply solutions, even small interventions, but with a higher level of scalability and transferability, and link the macro-micro stakeholders.

The final objective of the Milan pilot is to draw potential recommendations for a circular strategy to transition their urban food system towards becoming circular, also resulting in an increased citizen participation in circular material and product flows.

Thus, the pilot project sets out to focus on specific food flows to test new food prototypes, support existing projects that transform food waste into new products, and enable initiatives that focus on reducing food waste at the wholesale and market stage. With SO.GE.M.I. as a key player in the Milan pilot, there is a strong emphasis on building strong business cases. This focus is reflected in the pilot solutions developed which push forward a local sustainable food system in Milan through circular food innovations.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

Figure 4. Milan pilot city © REFLOW

An initial analysis was conducted on different city covered markets, such as the one in the Darsena neighborhood which also attracts tourists, the one in Morsenchio which is more relevant at the neighborhood scale, and the one in Corvetto which has already activated different participatory logics with local associations. Therefore, as the pilot markets are located in different areas of the city and they also differ within each other, it was possible to employ different activities.

Citizenship is then conceived as a collateral group to which proposals for involvement on individual experiments would arrive, even in the markets themselves which are places of aggregation, in some phases (laboratories, etc.). The “animated market” experience was a call by the administration on the markets, giving them the possibility during the period of the “Salone del Mobile” to organize education and awareness activities with NGOs and associations. Their intention was to outline this call on the themes of Reflow, to begin to approach circular economy matters in these places. However, this was no longer possible. Milan pilot is also working towards the 15 minutes city framework and in connecting associations with citizens, such as Recup that recovers waste in the weekly open air markets. Recup mainly works in open air markets (6 or 7), but with COVID-19 has also begun to collaborate in the SO.GE.MI. hub, the wholesale market. In both the open air markets and in the SO.GE.MI hub, volunteers help in the recovery of fruits and vegetables, and with the division and splitting. Especially in this period, people are motivated and interested in how it is possible to improve sustainability within the city, so it is fundamental to increase citizens' awareness.

Another interesting factor of the Milan pilot city is the connection with the economic dimension of the realities that work in the circular economy sphere. In this perspective, there is *Ibrida* that uses unsold bread as malt to produce beer. There is therefore visible economic logic in this process. This process can point out to citizens that even leftover bread has an economic value, and trigger in them the desire to join this chain. However, in order to increase civic engagement in the circular economy processes, this could also be somehow rewarded.

1.1.5 Vejle - Circular Plastics

City partners in Vejle defined four different physical scenarios where to test circular solutions on the plastic flows: *Sofiegården* - elderly care center, *REMA 1000* - supermarket chain, *Den Gamle Gård* - social housing building, and *Spinderihallerne* - entrepreneur and innovation hub.

The targeted stakeholders are citizens, public institutions, private companies, and entrepreneurs. At *Sofiegården*, city partners prototypes circular solutions to minimize the use of plastics. At *REMA 1000* partners investigate on the creation of circular loops and works in the entire value chain. *Den Gamle Gård* has almost 300 apartments and hosts a very diverse mix of citizens, from different socio-cultural backgrounds. Under these circumstances, circular economy and green transition are not in their priorities. Therefore, the aim is to create a community and showcase the importance of sorting the waste correctly. Interestingly, partners decided to leverage on the youngsters and let them translate the knowledge to adults. *Spinderihallerne*, the creative and innovation lab is a cultural place, and it is used as a hub of inspiration and to hold exhibitions. The Pilots efforts here are to work together with makers and citizens to create a biolab for experimentation as well as conduct several citizen involvement workshops and exhibitions. The final aim for pilot's work in the four test sites is to scale up the different solutions developed and tested at the test sites from the microscale level to the city and national level.

The approach has been to create solutions from a bottom-up approach strictly related to people’s needs and co-creative input. However, due to the different scenarios, the methods employed by city partners are different too. For instance, at *Den Gamle Gård*, the pilot set up a design thinking process to prototype solutions together with residents. Additionally, the local Resource Center conducted a waste analysis on plastic through collecting the material from the site, analyzing it, as well as conducting observations and qualitative interviews. Most importantly, a representative of the tenants is a member of the steering group, therefore directly involved in the decision-making process throughout the project implementation. To facilitate the prototyping phase, city partners invited experts from Denmark to present to residents some innovative ideas. Starting from these proposals, residents have developed and tested the new prototype. This initial process started in person, but then when Covid-19 hit hard in Denmark, it was all turned online. Accordingly, pilot city partners realized that the residents who were involved were mainly people already interested in topics such as waste and sorting - and it was hard to engage with a broader audience online.

Figure 5. Vejle pilot city © REFLOW

At *Spinderihallerne*, which attends different kinds of exhibitions and experiments, like workshops and events, and with different targets people, like schools, makers and entrepreneurs, had to close due to the lockdown. However, the first exhibition was showcased online. The second and final exhibition will be held in April and May 2022 in *Spinderihallerne*, and this will have a lot of engaging elements for citizens and students to participate in. At *Sofiegården*, solutions are targeted workers and the management personnel of the elderly care center. Similarly, at *REMA 1000* actions addressed mainly private companies.

1.1.6 Amsterdam - Textile (Life)Cycling

Amsterdam city pilot focuses on the circular textile wheel. The aim of the pilot is to increase the amount of collected textile in Amsterdam and open a collaboration with the industries to reduce the amount of virgin fibers that is being used. The pilot actions are two fold: producers and designers investigate and create new circular solutions; while, user’s and citizens focus on reducing, repairing and discarding correctly. In this regard, it is necessary to broaden the general knowledge of the textile flow. City partners, therefore, targeted designers, private companies, policy makers, and students.

Figure 6. Amsterdam city pilot © REFLOW

Aiming at raising citizen’s awareness on such a topic, dissemination activities to the civil society, as well as to the private sector is fundamental. *Pakhuis de Zweger*, a platform for social innovation and creation, and one of the pilot city partners, moderates online meetups, webinars or talks to everyone who wants to join. While, another pilot city partners, *WAAG*, a future lab for technology and society carry out workshops. These workshops were virtually conducted. Participants received an information guide and a toolkit and through moderators were taught on how to

produce new products by recycling textile. Importantly, also young students were targeted. Children between 8 and 12 years, in cooperation with the library of Amsterdam, attended courses about circular textiles. Another activity targeting youngsters, from the primary schools, is the *textile race*. Children would stroll around their districts and collect the textiles, directly from neighbors, which will be used in school projects. In total 15 schools have participated. Another solution will be the *swap shop*. It is a shop run by a social enterprise, where people can discard their textile in exchange for something in return. City partners aim to open 10 or 15 of these swap shops in various shops, libraries, and groceries. Another solution aims to extend also for the textile industry is the *stadspass*. *Stadspass* is a card dedicated to the less advantaged citizens, through which they can receive discounts for specific purchases. City partners would like to introduce tailors that could repair for free (for repairs not higher than 25 euro) clothes to the holders of the *stadspass*. Participants of the debates and the workshops, run by *Pakhuis de Zweger* and *WAAG*, were a mix of citizens or representative of the civil society more or less already engaged with circular economy and sustainability. City partners observed enthusiasm among youngsters and teenagers that were involved in the *textile race*. Schools, additionally, introduced compulsory classes on textile, and related issues and opportunities. Through this, they could put theory into practice. Interestingly, it was detected how the young students were also involving their parents in these activities.

1.1.7 Takeaways from the informal interviews

The first round of interviews was useful to acquire a main understanding of the pilot’s meaning and about the activities undertaken in the six Reflow city pilots since the beginning of the project. Here below are reported the main takeaways from the interviews. Additionally, similarities and contrasts were also identified.

Pilots, such as Cluj-Napoca and Amsterdam are aware and active in regard to sustainability and the circular economy. The same, with the addition of Vejle, since the project started have conducted citizen engagement activities at various levels: Vejle at Den Gamle Gård, an apartment building, focuses on creating better and more intuitive waste sorting and creating more commitment within the local community. Importantly, representatives of the tenants were included in the steering group of the pilot, hence, able to direct influence in the decision-making process. Amsterdam and Cluj-Napoca with the support of *Pakhuis de Zwijger*, *de WAAG* and the Innovation and Civic Imagination Center (CIIC) respectively, were able to engage with a broader audience through workshops and seminars. Importantly, partners from the city pilots, also, conducted activities with students: Amsterdam engaged with students from the primary and secondary schools; Cluj-Napoca introduced a course on energy efficiency and circular economy at the technological university. To notice, the same students live in the pilot building, in which the retrofit kit which is going to be implemented and used as a case study in the course.

On the contrary, cities such Milan and Berlin have changed their initial plans and strategies. The former was thinking of putting the food market at the center of their engagement strategies. However, also due to Covid-19 and safety restrictions, and the different priorities of the food market sellers back then, pilot city partners decided to work with a higher-level stakeholders, such as SO.GE.MI, AMSA and the food policy. Besides that, with the help of the FabLab and the involvement of other entities, such as start-ups and associations, some initial experiments and prototypes were showcased at the markets to the community. While, Berlin city partners have delayed the activities, due to a double change in the municipal partner, which also caused a change in the material flow object of the city pilot.

Other commonalities were found between Berlin and Paris city pilots. The activities focus on very specific material flows, such the wastewater heat in Berlin and wood for temporary use in Paris. Therefore, engaging citizens on such topics, which are considered as niche, was more challenging.

1.2 Online workshop

On the 3rd of May 2021 as the last part of this first phase of the Citizen Engagement and Capacity Building Strategies task, an online workshop with the pilot city's partners was conducted. The final objective of this workshop was to let the pilots reflect on what phases of the materials cycle the engagement of the citizen is undergoing and in which one would be most valuable. Aware of the different starting points of the city pilots, and that they are all experimenting innovative solutions, the ambition of the workshop was to use together some moments to exchange some ideas and insights on how to improve the citizen engagement under the pandemic situation. Precisely, the aim was to understand how citizens can be involved in the city pilot activities: on one hand to improve its quality, on the other hand to ensure long-term sustainability.

The image shows a screenshot of a presentation slide from the Reflow project. It features the Reflow logo in the top left corner and a close button (X) in the top right. The slide title is "T.5.5. Citizens engagement and community building strategies". The agenda items are listed below:

- 14.00 - 14.30 - **Welcoming and Plenary introduction**
- 14.30 - 15.00 - **Step 1 - Material Flow Replication and Citizen Engagement (Individual)**
- 15.00 - 15.30 - **Plenary (3mins each)**
- 15.30 - 15.45 - **Coffee break**
- 15.45 - 16.30 - **Step 2 - Level of Participation and Possible New Strategies (G: Milan, Vejile, Amsterdam D: Cluj, Paris, Berlin)**
- 16.30 - 17.00 - **Plenary and Closing**

Figure 7. Schedule of the online workshop moderated on the 3rd of May 2021

The workshop was composed of two main steps:

1. **Material flow replication and citizen engagement:** in the first step, partners, individually, were invited to make or draw a diagram showing what is the status of their material flow in one or more aspect under analysis. Partners were invited to choose one solution, among the ones that were experimenting, which were considered as the most relevant at that moment, or maybe the one more advanced or that needed a deeper investigation. The idea was to have a very simple diagram showing the flow of the material and the identification of the steps in which interaction with people occurred.
2. **Level of participation and possible new strategies:** In this second step, participants were divided in two groups with colleagues from other pilot cities. The two groups were divided as follows: Milan, Vejle and Berlin and Paris, Amsterdam, and Cluj (could not attend the workshop). Participants, starting from the outcome of the first step, were invited to discuss with one another on how to improve the citizen engagement and to think how citizens could take over some parts of the pilot activities.

For each of the two groups additional information and ideas for future activities, coming from a collective discussion, were added to the previous diagram.

Here below, screenshots from the miro board used during the online workshop display the exercise undertaken by the pilot members during the first step.

1.2.1 Berlin - Waste Heat

Berlin pilot partners have listed the key target groups for engagement at the moment, owners and managers of public properties, developers, city planners, and managers of industrial parks. By focusing on them the solution could have a greater impact, then focusing only on raising citizens’ awareness. During the exercise pilot representatives confirmed that the showcase of the solution at the CityLab and the workshops and training programme as valid solutions that could help to reach out the target groups previously listed.

Figure 8. Online workshop results from Berlin pilot city

1.2.2 Paris - Fair Tracker

During the exercise Paris city partners decided to start from an event and the subsequent deconstruction of the furniture. Later on the material is stored and reused in another event. Starting from this general and non-circular loop of the material in object, participants listed the different solutions that have been tested in the pilot activities, like “re-label”, “circular making course” and the exhibition made from reused wood.

Additionally, key targets were identified for each of the solutions being tested in the pilot city.

Figure 9. Online workshop results from Paris city pilot

1.2.3 Milan - Food Market 4.0

Milan city partners have described three different scenarios: the first one is about the development and co-design with strategic stakeholders, such as AMSA and SO.GE.MI, of a “Food Market 4.0” dashboard to better manage and control the material flows of different products inside the food markets. The second scenario, instead, is called “Foody Zero Waste”. In this scenario the NGO RECUP plays an important role by saving and collecting the unsold food within Foody (fruit and vegetable wholesale market in SO.GE.M.I) in the market and having the connection with various local stakeholders. The last scenario is called “Milano Prima Seconda” and is an exchange system of resources, specifically among bakeries at neighborhood level and the startup named “Ibrida”. The latter connects bakeries and local breweries that produce beer with the unsold bread instead of using normal malt.

Figure 10. Online workshop results from Milan city pilot

1.2.4 Vejle - Circular Plastics

Representatives from Vejle, in this exercise, decided to focus on *Sofiegården*, the elderly care center. They identified three main scenarios: procurement policy and contracts, food packaging and diapers. Per each of the three thematics, specific targeted stakeholders were determined.

Concerning the food packaging, representatives thought to look for different products, more sustainable, and therefore market research could be employed. In regards to the residents of the health care center, the aim is to raise awareness on the usage, and especially, on the disposal of the used materials. And lastly, by focusing on the public procurement sphere, the aim is to work on the policy level and change the contracts that define the suppliers of the health care center.

Figure 11. Online workshop results from Vejle city pilot

1.2.5 Amsterdam - Textile (Life)Cycling

Participants from the city of Amsterdam decided to conduct this exercise on the *denim deal*. The *denim deal* gathers the different denim brands committed to a certain amount of recycled content in the final product that they sell.

Therefore, in the exercise, city partners reproduced the denim cycle starting from consumers that wear the denim, that should be educated to wear them for longer, reducing the amount of denim discarded. However, when discarded will, then, be sorted and shredded and then transformed into new yarns. These last goes to the manufacturers that, through the addition of new denim, create a new product.

The different steps of the denim cycle were then linked with the activities undergoing in the city pilot, linking respectively the targeted stakeholders.

Figure 12. Online workshop results from Amsterdam city pilot

1.2.6 Cluj-Napoca - PLEnergy

Figure 13. Online workshop results from Cluj-Napoca city pilot

Representatives from Cluj-Napoca could not attend the online workshop. Therefore, the exercise was independently done offline by the city partners in the following days. The main problem for which pilot city partners aim to find a solution is the outdated and not well-functioning energy infrastructure, with no consumption monitoring system. Firstly, a consultation among the different pilot city partners was conducted: the technical school, Municipality of Cluj-Napoca, ARIES and ITIM. This was then, followed by a few design meetings. During the design meetings, city partners designed a

retrofitting kit to be tested in one of the dormitor for students from the technical school. This solution also represents a case study for the same. The main pilot city objective is to increase awareness about energy efficiency, targeting students, tenants, but also public administration for adopting energy efficiency and circular solutions.

Follows a short summary of the collective discussion within the two groups in the second step of the workshop. In which, city partners were asked to discuss the level of participation and where citizens could take over some of the activities in the pilot solutions.

1.2.7 Group 1 (Milan - Food Market 4.0, Vejle - Circular Plastics, Berlin - Waste Heat)

In the common discussion, Milan city partners focused on the challenges related to the three scenarios: food waste prevention, secondary raw materials, and upcycling of waste. For instance, the main challenge was how the central food distribution center and local stakeholders could be involved in the development of models to reduce food waste and tracking food flows. Amongst the ideas that were suggested was to create small events to involve NGOs and citizens, to activate a real commitment and engagement. Pilot city partners, for the scenario “Milano Prima Seconda” and the engagement of the start up “Ibrida”, suggested the involvement of the student community that could be interested in drinks with ethical and environmental values.

Partners from Vejle, instead, set the discussion around the possibility of conducting awareness campaigns that could reach a broader community commitment. From the communal discussion, a suggestion that came out was the creation of an exhibition and the use of social media to raise its awareness in the city. This could be beneficial in opening a public debate on the value of the plastic.

Lastly, Berlin city pilots, similar to Milan, were focusing their action at a higher level of stakeholders. In this regard, ideas that emerged from the group discussion were the possibility to involve laundry shops, and the involvement of the in-house energy company of Berlin to circulate questionnaires to users, in order to gather data on awareness and needs. Importantly, in order to raise awareness on a specific topic as - waste water heat - to a broader audience, partners have developed a series of videos which simplify the technology.

1.2.8 Group 2 (Amsterdam - Textile (Life)Cycling; Paris - Fair Tracker)

One of the main challenges in Amsterdam is to create a successful awareness campaign. An awareness campaign able to reach over a million of residents is costly, and the Municipality cannot invest that much. Similarly, in New York, The Ellen MacArthur Foundation has conducted an awareness campaign with the municipality of New York. City partners in Amsterdam, were able to engage lots of local stakeholders and citizens in different solutions, and local stakeholders were looking for funds or ideas to use all this network involved as a benefit to engage with a broader population.

Additionally, various suggestions were drawn in regard to the Paris city partners. For instance, the entrepreneurs that organize the “Textile race”, in the pilot case of Amsterdam, also do the “EU waste race”, in which organizers and youngsters open mobile phones and sort the components. Therefore, this could also be replicated for other materials, such as wood. Another good example proposed to the pilot partners from Paris was the “stadshout” - city wood. *Stadshout* creates new furniture and other materials out of old trees that need to be cut, and then materials are sold back to citizens. Fundamental in the Paris pilot solutions is the smart storage. City partners were thinking of developing a database able to share resources from shops, or other businesses which gather re-usable wood and make this data available online. In this the “do it yourself” shops could be involved to give the workspace, workshops, or to collect, and store the materials.

1.3 On-line survey

In November 2021, pilot city partners received, through a google form, a request to compile an online questionnaire. The compiling of the questionnaire, in which city partners could update with their pilot experimentation in the solutions where it was foreseen an active involvement of citizens, constituted additional information for the deliverable in object.

Particularly, to pilot city partners was asked to give further information for each of the proposed solutions that was going to be tested in their pilot, and in which citizens were understood as “prosumers” in a sharing economy perspective. In details, to city partners was asked:

- Brief description of the solution/s;
- Scale of the intervention/s;
- Key actors involved;
- General improvements;
- Citizens’ role;
- Citizens’ benefit/s;
- and possible obstacles.

The questionnaire remained open for partners until a few days before the project meeting scheduled on the 19th-20th of January. *Table 3* shows a short summary of the responses from the 6 Reflow pilot cities.

Table 3. Summary of the questionnaire responses

City Pilot	Name of the solution	Brief description	General improvements	Key actors involved	Citizen’s role	Citizens’ benefit	Obstacles
<i>Paris - Fair Tracker</i>	RE-Label	Re-Label offers a toolbox of tools and services to local makers to better valorise their work, reduce the generation of wood scraps, increase reuse of those scraps that are unavoidable, and increase sales. The improved valorisation is made possible by offering a certificate for the product, which shows the specificities and singularities of their creation. The information includes origin, measurements, history, quality of the material, and time spent by the maker, and is gathered in the Re-	Re-Label works on coordinating the community and improving collaboration around exchanges of ideas and best practices. This includes a catalog of cutting files, which shows a library of useful/necessary shapes allowing the establishment of a decentralized stock of pre-cut parts, in order to avoid the scraps.	Entrepreneurs, Private companies, Public companies	The citizens are involved by their role as consumers: they have a better understanding of what they are buying and they can be actors of change.	Better consumption, more accessibility of information about what they buy. Also an online platform to have access to sustainable and ethical products.	Have the designers/makers respect the protocol.

		Label certificate edited by an online generator. The document is dated and signed by the designer or the workshop manager.					
Vejle - Circular Plastics	Den Gamle Gård - New sorting solutions	The residents are testing new integrated sorting solutions in their own kitchens. Wild Studios will design flower pots made from reused household plastics that will be set up at an event at Den Gamle Gård in the spring 2022.	The new solution will make it easier to connect sorting from the kitchen to the containers in the yard - this will help improve the sorting rate and move the plastic out of the residual waste. Moreover the residents will be made more aware of waste and that it is possible to make new products out of household plastic waste. And so, through our activities they will understand what a circular economy is in practice.	Entrepreneurs, Association, Civil society, Private companies, Public companies	By letting the citizens test the solutions in the apartments, we ensure that it is valuable and useful in practice. The test participants represent different target groups.	The integrated solutions will make sorting more intuitive and they gain a lot of new knowledge through working with the REFLOW team.	Getting in contact with the test participants and collecting (qualitative) data during the test phase.

	Spinderihallerne - bioplastic workshop	Workshop with “ <i>Materiom</i> ” focusing on biomaterials in theory and practice.	Informative workshops on how to work with biomaterials will communicate and raise awareness among participants. The workshop can be used in practice (especially business wise)	Entrepreneurs, Association, Civil society, Private companies, Public companies	Involvement of citizens is important for a satisfactory participation in the workshop	They gain knowledge and tools to work with bio-based materials in theory and practice	Reaching out to citizens and relevant stakeholders to make sure they want to participate
	Spinderihallerne - awareness campaign	The exhibition will communicate the REFLOW project in Vejle and how companies, designers and artists work with plastic as a resource.	The aim is to raise awareness and gain knowledge among all visitors	Entrepreneurs, Association, NGOs, Civil society, Private companies, Public companies	The exhibition will communicate the REFLOW project in Vejle and how companies, designers and artists work with plastic as a resource.	They gain knowledge through a physical and sensory exhibition. Hopefully they get inspired and reorganizes/optimize practices in relation to plastics and better sorting	Attracting visitors and involving different stakeholders and citizens (if Covid-19 closes everything down again)
Amsterdam - Textile (Life)Cycling	Swapshop	The citizens are the customers of the Swapshop. Swapshop gives them the opportunity to exchange clothing for little money. They compete with low cost fast fashion brands.	Longevity of clothing, extending lifetime - compete with Fast fashion brands.	Entrepreneurs, NGOs, Civil society, Public companies	Citizens are the customers of the Swapshop, if there is more demand for places like Swapshop they can extend their services in terms of opening new locations.	The Swapshop gives them the opportunity to exchange clothing for little money.	Second hand clothing is often perceived as not clean.

	On demand textile collecting	Pantar is a social enterprise that provides work for those that are distant from the labor market. Together with the municipality they provide a service to collect discarded textiles at homes of people living in the city center.	Better collecting of textile, less textile in normal trash bin. Textiles will also be sorted by Pantar to enable better textile recycling.	NGOs, Civil society	More engagement, awareness will lead to more and better collecting	On demand enables collecting textile from their homes, it is an extra service to make it easier for people to discard textiles properly.	Citizens don't use the on demand service due to lack of communication/awareness creation of this service.
	Stadspas	This service enables citizens with a lower income to repair their clothes and extend the longevity of their items. It improves their cost of living.	People will repair their clothes more often and this will result in less discarding.	Civil society, Private companies	Citizens are the targeted customers.	Discount for repairing clothes for citizens while the tailors receive 100% payment.	Price of the discount for repair is leading if the solution will succeed.
Cluj-Napoca - PLEnergy	Retrofit Kit	The solution is to implement a retrofit kit along with a smart metering system in a publicly-owned building (school dormitory + auxiliary buildings such as laundry and offices) to both	Greatly improve consumer behavior when it comes to energy consumption.	Teachers, students	Citizens can be a major factor for promoting the solution city-wide.	Less expenses with energy bills and better quality of energy use (e.g. brighter light in the offices thanks to LED lighting).	Lack of awareness from the users, covid-19 restrictions.

		increase energy efficiency and influence consumer behavior by raising awareness of users (teachers, students and other users).					
	Energy Tree	The ENERGY TREE is an integrative solution which demonstrates the co-production of energy from alternative sources and as an output has information and public-services (small scale energy and wi-fi).	It improves the awareness of citizens regarding energy efficiency and green and circular energy situation and options in the city.	Association, Civil society, Private companies	Citizens can participate in a poll to determine what the most interesting output-services are for them.	Increase awareness, obtain public services of wifi and charging phones etc.	The greatest challenge is funding the prototyping of this solution.
	Curricula for Circular Economy	A curriculum for MA level course on Circular Economy.	It is the first course of its kind to be offered in Romania to our knowledge.	University, students	Input and feedback on the course.	Future Skills acquisition.	How to offer the practical applicability in the Romanian context.
Milan - Food Market 4.0	Food market 4.0 dashboard	Food Market 4.0 Dashboard is an integrated system of Hw/Sw elements to allow the tracking and monitoring of inbound and	Tracking food flows makes it possible to reduce food waste. If scaled at city level it can contribute to the circularity of the food supply chain.	Entrepreneurs, Private companies, Public companies	The massive involvement of citizens will allow us to generate accurate data about circular food behaviors.	As part of the civil society they will be beneficiaries of the circularity of the food supply chain produced by the implementation of the solution.	A challenge could be the development of the digital skills of the market vendor involved, as a starting point of a strategy able to

		<p>outbound goods from the Municipal Markets. Citizens are involved as market customers. Moreover, as part of the civil society they are also beneficiaries of the circularity of the food supply chain produced by the implementation of the solution.</p>					<p>combine digital transformation and circular transition for Municipal Covered Markets.</p>
<p>Berlin - Waste Heat</p>	<p>Sourcing energy consumption data</p>	<p>We are approaching the actors in order to source intel about energy consumption of properties, thereby triggering interest in a more sustainable way of heating.</p>	<p>More awareness about waste heat methods and actually providing a path to go circular in terms of heating.</p>	<p>Private companies, Public companies</p>	<p>The more information about energy consumption data we get, the better.</p>	<p>Their properties are becoming more sustainable.</p>	<p>Difficulty to understand and to relate to.</p>

1.3.1 Overall citizens experience in the piloting experimentation

The six pilot cities have undertaken various activities and prototyped different solutions for a more circular urban metabolism. Solutions were of different nature. Some were more technological and digitally-oriented, while others were physical interventions. Additionally, all the city pilots also run various co-designing workshops and awareness campaigns in order to reach a broader audience in their piloting activities.

Most importantly, a broad variety of stakeholders were involved: entrepreneurs, public and private companies, associations, civil society and NGOs, of which with different roles and benefits.

2 The role of citizens in enabling a circular economy transition

Circular Economy (CE) has emerged as a paradigm, highlighting multiple paths and targets to attain sustainable development, and to propose ways to create value for customers, societies, and other stakeholders. Moreover, the understanding of CE has attracted increasing research interest, and it is currently mainstreamed in several stakeholders, from municipal to national governments, academia, and businesses around the world, and has become a policy tool to move forward sustainability.

CE puts forward the concept of developing new business models that transform traditional linear economies of “take, make, dispose”, into an alternative flow model, one that is circular and looking for closed loops. It has been argued that circular materials reduce negative environmental impacts, by minimizing the consumption of virgin materials and energy, and stimulating new business opportunities. However, CE views have privileged economic solutions as the driver for solving material and energy-related problems, rather than a sustainability paradigm, which should require a complete mapping of three sustainability dimensions. Indeed, although sustainability has, as a main goal, to benefit the environment, the economy, and the society at large, the current main beneficiaries of CE appear to be economic actors that implement the system.

Notwithstanding a few voices from authors advocating for the inclusion of social aspects in CE concepts, tools, and metrics, the concept of CE today clearly appears to prioritize the economic system with primary benefits for the environment, either resource efficiency or environmental efficiency, and only implicit gains for social aspects. Major social aspects that reside in the CE are social inclusion, local democracy, employment, sharing and collaborative economy and participation.

Here below there will be presented various tools, methods and models that further strengthen the role of citizens in enabling circular economy transition and the related social aspects. Some of the instruments and best practices that will be presented, on one hand, are more top-down, as a meaning for consultation and information. On the other hand, there will be some more bottom-up practices, inherited as local or civic initiatives, aiming at deliberation and co-creation.

2.1 Tools and methods for citizens’ participation

To begin with, we will be sharing some basic and general knowledge on how to promote and conduct participatory processes, paying particular attention to the physical, cultural, and social identities that define a scenario and support its ongoing evolution. Participatory processes, with community-based at its center, contribute to people's health, happiness, and well-being. However, public participation processes may raise questions on how to engage people and how to ensure a diverse group of participants.

1. Create participation possibilities for different target groups such as families, kids, youth, elderly people, people with special needs, immigrants, and consider different groups' time schedules and needs. Make sure to be inclusive for people with mental and physical disabilities, parents who may need childcare, people who may struggle with the local

- language and create a safe space for marginalized people. Think about digital and in person participation possibilities to be truly inclusive.
2. Include low thresholds for participation so it's easy to take part in. Having a cup of coffee during a pop-up café and chatting about one's experience in a neighborhood is an example of participation that does not require much effort yet may be very valuable in how to develop a participatory process.
 3. Consider pay-offs for participation. While it may be feasible for engaged and dedicated people to spend a lot of time, resources, and energy investing in engaging, this may not be the case for all people. Hence, creating a variety of pay-offs such as free snacks and drinks, or a nice hangout spot with music are possibilities to create rewards for people's time and engagement. Working together with students, credits for courses may be a way to engage them.
 4. Financial compensation and the creation of green jobs for young people is another possibility to create a pay-off. Creating green and social jobs is relevant for creating a sustainable present and future and is a great way to build the capacity of new leaders. Creating financial payoffs for youth working in the project team seems fair given their time and dedication whereas lower threshold participation should rather not be financially compensated.
 5. Listen, learn, exchange, facilitate, and collaborate. Creating change in a local community is challenging as diverse people with diverse ideas, needs, and wishes may contradict each other. Listening is the first important step in successfully tackling people. What would they like to engage in? Learn from them and exchange your experience, knowledge, and skills. Facilitated co-creation workshops and a broad range of participatory methods can contribute to creating change.
 6. Be available and share what you learned from your local communication. Use different platforms and communicate addressing your different target groups. Would you like to hear people's opinions? Do you want to tell the story about what happened after their collaboration? Think about different forums and ways of addressing them. You may want to communicate both on social media as well as through posters, newspaper articles, and flyers. Talking to people and inviting them to bring along friends, neighbors and family is a way to reach out to people that are illicit or do not speak the local language.
 7. Make sure you have a plan for integrating public participation in your participatory process and it will have an impact. No matter if you ask for ideas, or invite the community to do something, it's important to let them know how you will care for their work.

In the paragraphs that follows, diverse tools, experimental participatory methods and models will be presented.

2.1.1 Digital tools

The aforementioned suggestions could be considered in attending a physical process, although as said also digital tools can and should be considered. Especially since the pandemic turned the world upside down and the shelter-in-place order was issued globally, it is necessary to find ways to advance participatory practices under unprecedented circumstances, in order not to let the public safety restrictions curb participation.

The introduction of digital and mobile technologies has profoundly changed everyday life, transforming the way people communicate and interact with one another, but also the way of consuming or producing services and experiencing places. In this regard, two relatively new ways of citizen engagement have gained popularity: e-participation and gamification practices. E-participation refers to the technology-mediated interaction between the civil society sphere

and the formal politics sphere¹. Gamification practices concern the mobilization and implementation of ludic elements in order to manage “real” issues and affect human behavior². Additionally, playing usually does not require specific knowledge, allowing a greater variety of participants.

[greenApes](#) and [Stadtsache](#) are two clear examples of apps that collect data on sustainable behaviors and about people’s opinions. Greenapes is a digital platform rewarding sustainable actions and ideas. Cities can choose the behaviors they would like to reward (green mobility, waste sorting, energy savings, participation and volunteering). By doing and sharing their actions, citizens’ will get prizes and at the same time inspire others. [Stadsache](#) is also a digital app, focused on children. It is an innovative tool for collecting photos, sounds, videos or recording paths. The app gives specific tasks and actions and the result is shared with other users of the app. The collected experiences and materials will gradually create a map that makes children and young people visible as city experts. These experiences, also, provide data to authorities and urban practitioners about citizens’ sustainable behaviors and perceptions, especially from youngsters, of the urban living environments. Another example is the case active in Bristol, [Hello Lamp Post](#)¹, where a QR code is attached on urban objects in the street, and by scanning that code you can start chatting with these objects that they will reply you with some pre-set questions about the surrounding area and through that the municipality is collecting and storage data about citizens’ opinions, suggestions or ideas.

Some suggestions for the Reflow pilot cases, even though relevant for all it could be in particular for:

- Berlin: the digital tools could be very useful to be integrated as tests developed within the City Lab expo area;
- Cluj: the digital tools could be integrated to visualize the implementation of the toolkits;

2.1.2 Participatory platform

As previously said, practitioners should also consider the use of different platforms and the communication addressing different target groups. Additionally, this goes hand-to-hand with the digital innovation in which we are all involved.

[Decidim](#) is a web environment (a framework) produced in Ruby on Rails that allows users to create and configure a website platform or portal, to be used in the form of a social network, for democratic participation. The portal allows any organization (local city council, association, university, NGO, trade union, neighborhood or cooperative) to create massive democratic processes for strategic planning, participatory budgeting, collaborative regulatory design, urban spaces design and elections. It also enables the organization of in-person meetings, signing up for them, the publication of minutes, proposing points for the agenda and receiving notifications of the results. Decidim can also help organizing governing bodies, councils or assemblies, the convening of consultations and referendums or channeling citizen or member initiatives to impact different decision-making processes. All together Decidim makes possible to digitally structure a complete system of participatory democratic governance for any organization.

Decidim operates within two different levels: participatory spaces, and components. The former are the frameworks that define how participation will be carried out, the channels or means through which citizens or members of an organization can process requests or coordinate proposals and make decisions. These are, for instance, initiatives, processes, assemblies and consultations. While the latter are the participatory mechanisms that allow a series of

¹ Saad-Sulonen, J. (2012). The role of the creation and sharing of digital media content in participatory e-planning. *International Journal of E-Planning Research*, 1(2), 1-22. doi:10.4018/ijep.2012040101

² Vanolo, A. (2018). Cities and the politics of gamification. *Cities*, 74, 320-326. doi:10.1016/j.cities.2017.12.021

operations and interactions between the platform users within each of the participatory spaces, such as, comments, proposals, votes, debates, surveys, blogs, newsletters or meetings.

2.1.3 Participatory democracy

Other methods being used, this time more top-down than the others, are the citizens assembly. A **citizens' assembly** is a new form of democracy which allows the making of decisions at a city, national or even at the international level by a randomly selected group of residents according to the demographic criteria such as age and gender. It constitutes a city or a country in miniature.

A role of a citizens' assembly is an in-depth analysis of a given issue, a deliberation over different solutions, hearing of the pros and cons, and then, making informed decisions. It guarantees:

1. High-quality decision developed with involvement of citizens;
2. Common goods are at the heart of the process;
3. Decisions are developed by an independent group of citizens, thanks to the process of random selection;
4. Decisions are made after learning about the issue and listening to people with diverse perspectives. The process includes deliberation phase and consultations with experts;
5. High level of consent for decisions made – at least 80 percent support of the citizens' assembly;
6. The process of organizing a citizens' assembly encourages institutions and organizations to search for solutions and to prepare their recommendations;
7. New possibilities and solutions may appear thanks to the nature of the process, which involves presentation of a wide range of views and perspectives;
8. and lastly, it is a transparent way of making decisions.

Some suggestions for the Reflow pilot cases, even though relevant for all it could be in particular for:

- Milan: the platform could be integrated within the functionalities of the Reflow project in order to develop an engagement of citizens and stakeholders;
- Vejle: could be an opportunity to engage citizens and stakeholders in the five scenarios for circular plastics.

2.1.4 Cooperative model

Another interesting model to engage with citizens, and empower them with shared responsibility, is the activation of a **cooperative**. A cooperative is an association of persons (organization) that is owned and controlled by the people to meet their common economic, social, and/or cultural needs and aspirations through a jointly-owned and democratically controlled business. Here it will present one case we came across during one research from [Eutropian](#), an organisation providing support with advocacy, research and policy to support inclusive urban processes- Funding the cooperative city. Community finance and the economy of civic spaces³- the [Afrikaanderwijk Cooperative](#).

Afrikaanderwijk cooperative operates in South Rotterdam's Feijenoord area. Evolved from an art project conducted in the area by the Freehouse Foundation, and then in 2013, they set up the Afrikaanderwijk Cooperative, an umbrella

³ Patti, D., Polyak L., (2017): Funding the Cooperative City: Community Finance and the Economy of Civic Spaces. Cooperative City Books, Vienna.

organization, and handed over all the activities and the cooperative work spaces to the cooperative. It brings together existing workspaces, entrepreneurs, producers, social organizations and the food market. The cooperative began its work by mapping the unrecognized skills and competences of residents in the Afrikaanderwijk neighborhood, suffering from problems of low education, unemployment and a bad reputation. The goal of this neighborhood cooperative is to stimulate sustainable local production and entrepreneurship, by developing local skills and setting up chains of collective production.

They started with the regeneration of the market, and then began to zoom out into the wider area. They came across a lot of people who were part of strong informal networks. Many people were working in food production, but they couldn't really sell or earn money with their skills because they didn't have professional kitchens. There was an empty kitchen in the neighborhood so they created access for these home cooks to the kitchen so that they could start organizing a catering service together. Similarly, with the Neighborhood Kitchen, they set up Home Cooks Feijenoord, a meal service for elderly, sick, and disabled people where professionals and volunteers prepare meals in people's homes.

Besides the kitchen, they have another cooperative space for textile production that works the same way, creates room for people to meet, and gets people involved into what is going on in the area, contributing to the local economy. Because of the presence of many people with specific skills and talents in knitting, they bring them together in the sewing studio that works for fashion designers and other commissions. Additionally, they don't just focus on culture production anymore but also start up new businesses. In fact, they started a cleaning company called SCHOON that ensures that cleaning work that normally is outsourced to companies elsewhere is “insourced” and carried out by members of the Afrikaanderwijk Workers Co-op. Now people living in the area clean 80% of the buildings owned by the area's main housing agency.

They also rent out the Gemaal op Zuid to commercial, governmental and private parties that allow them financially to share the space with locally based co-op members and inhabitants, as a space for presentations, exhibitions, meetings, dinners, workshops, knowledge exchange and so on. Lastly, it was also established as an energy collective that made it possible to buy energy collectively, realizing substantial savings for businesses in the neighborhood and also looking into the possibility of helping households with our collective buying power. From all these different flows of money, their revenue, 50% goes to their members, 25% goes back to the cooperative and 25% goes into funds for social and cultural projects. Importantly, in order to lock money flows in the neighborhood, you don't really have to scale up but strengthen local networks and connect them to networks outside the area.

Some suggestions for the Reflow pilot cases, even though relevant for all it could be in particular for:

- Amsterdam: the cooperative model is in synergy with the textile (life) cycling;
- Milan: the model could be applied for some of the scenarios to engage the local neighborhood, for example for the beer production.

2.1.5 Crowdfunding & crowdsourcing

Other methods that will be presented are **crowdfunding** and **crowdsourcing**. They differentiate among each other mainly for the end result. With **crowdfunding**, people are looking specifically to raise money from the crowd. With crowdsourcing, people are seeking pretty much anything else: information, work, talent, skills, etc. More specifically, Crowdfunding is an excellent way for groups and people who don't have access to sources of or need for large amounts

of capital — like big investors or bank loans — to raise money. **Crowdsourcing** is more varied. At the most basic level, crowdsourcing is using the knowledge and power of the crowd to speed up a process.

Here follow four different platforms for crowdfunding and crowdsourcing, each of them with different characteristics. Those are: **Brickstarter**, **Spacehive**, **Goteo**, and **Tudigo**.

2.1.5.1 Brickstarter

Brickstarter is a platform for crowdfunding and crowdsourcing architectural projects, initiated by Bryan Boyer and Dan Hill, and realized within the Finnish Innovation Fund, Sitra. Brickstarter was conceived as an experiment to test the possibilities of opening the design and development of urban environments, to reduce the opacity of urban development processes and to create communication between various urban stakeholders. It started due to the recognition that an increasing number of people had a desire to be involved in shaping the city, and that a growing number of platforms, experimenting with crowdfunding and crowdsourcing, were emerging.

Founders were looking at using crowdfunding as a way to effectively vote by allocating some portion of taxes. Brickstarter is a platform that is run by a municipality or potentially by a central government, used as a participatory budgeting, to give people a means to have a more direct impact on the way that a portion of their tax money is being distributed. Brickstarter arises out of a desire to make the process of urban development more legible, and in doing so to enable a more diverse public to not only have a voice, but to actively contribute in shaping the city.

2.1.5.2 Spacehive

Spacehive came about in 2012 because the founder and CEO Chris Gourley, a journalist at the time covering planning and architecture within London, saw a real need in the market for something that facilitated a bottom-up transformation, civic participation in urban planning. It is a civic crowdfunding platform based in London.

Spacehive, also, works with councils as well as corporations as otherwise they tend to work in isolation, by putting all their energy resources into making one project. They help them to combine their resources, by giving everyone an active stake in making the project happen, and by doing this they develop a more sustainable funding model. This way people feel they have more ownership over what is happening in their communities. Importantly, one of their eligibility guidelines is that the project has to be available for the community to use, it has to be in a public space or have public access.

The platform, established in 2012, besides collecting donations from individuals, Spacehive also connects initiatives with funding sources including city councils, companies and grant-makers who are actively looking for projects in their specific areas of interest and so we match them intelligently. Therefore, if someone came along with a project about creating green spaces and he uploaded it to our website they would then encourage him to pitch that to all the different grant funders who are interested in funding green space. In this case, crowdfunding plays a part by getting people to have a say and creating that bottom-up democratization of choosing what is important and how you want your city to grow.

2.1.5.3 Goteo

Goteo is a platform for civic crowdfunding founded by Platoniq, a Catalan association of culture producers and software developers. Goteo helps citizen initiatives as well as social, cultural and technological projects that produce open-source

results and community benefits, with crowdfunding and crowdsourcing resources. More precisely, Goteo is a platform for crowdfunding campaigns, but it is not limited to funding: it also involves crowdsourcing. They, also, collect non-economic contributions that a community can help with, and in sharing open-sourced collective benefits for the community, allowing projects to be replicated, reused, disseminated, or even improved or copied for further uses.

In assessing the project, they look for two ways of rewarding. They divide rewards into two groups: one consists of individual rewards, referring to when a person economically supports the project and receives something back. The other refers to collective incentives that push the community to support a project and add social importance to it. When something feels important and adds value to society, it is likely that more people will support and engage with it. Interestingly, Goteo promotes its partners to also share their non-monetary needs in the community. In regards to monetary contributions, the particularity is that public institutions double the amount given by citizens; so for each euro made through crowdfunding, the administration offers another euro. It is a way to open the process of decision-making: there are initiatives that institutions would not fund without collective support.

2.1.5.4 Tudigo

Tudigo (ex-Bulb in Town) is a French crowdfunding platform established in 2012 by Alexandre Laing and Stéphane Vromman. Labeled as the first “local crowdfunding” site, it supports initiatives ranging from the creation of local shops and small businesses to the revitalisation of factories and the construction of energy plants, focusing on projects that have an important territorial impact. It is a platform where small businesses can find the funds they need to start and grow their business through the support of the local crowd, therefore people who have a direct interest in these businesses. This platform is adapted for small local businesses that do not have the skills to make crowdfunding campaigns happen. Interestingly, it is not just a funding tool, but also a very powerful engagement platform, because all the local people that are backing and funding projects also become the ambassadors of the projects.

The particularity of the Tudigo platform is that they have two different types of funding options. One is called reward-based funding, a Kickstarter-like crowdfunding process where people fund a particular business in exchange for a product or a service this business can provide. The second model is equity-based crowdfunding where people become investors in the selected business.

The other part of their vision, at the core of local crowdfunding, is citizen engagement, people engaging with their territory and connecting with its businesses. Crowdfunding begins when there is already a project. But before that, there is another kind of crowdsourcing. They developed another application connected to Tudigo, a tool called “Reveal” that helps launching challenges, questions to the community, like “What do you want to see in this neighborhood, what services and shops do you want?”. And, additionally, it can also be used for allocating money from a city’s budget, or as a digital tool for participatory budgeting.

Some suggestions for the Reflow pilot cases, even though relevant for all it could be in particular for:

- Paris: crowdfunding and crowdsourcing could be useful for the fair tracking of furniture, storage and available skills;
- Milan: crowdfunding could be useful for the development of pilot cases to engage the citizens.

3 Policy recommendations for citizens’ participation in circular economy transition

Derived from the six pilot cities experiences in regards to citizens engagement, we propose six key recommendations targeting policy makers and municipalities for citizens’ participation in the circular economy transition. These were drawn by considering the different dimensions of REFLOW: materials flows and tracking of data, technology and platforms, urban dimension, and network of social innovators and entrepreneurs. This last part was also thought to be disseminated separately, therefore, for this purpose it has been created an appendix titled “*Circular Citizens Handbook*” (*Appendix 1*).

3.1 Recommendation 1

Digital technologies are an enabler for the upscaling of the circular economy as they allow the creation and processing of data and information required for circular business models and the complex demands of circular supply chains. However, the circular economy is based on a strong integration and connection of the value chain as quality and predictability gain in importance. Therefore, digital technologies provide the basis for the development of circular business models. Additionally, the digital part of the business determines feasibility, usability and customer (or rather user) satisfaction⁴.

Importantly, according to the European Circular Economy Research Alliance (2020), the use of digital technology see the application in three main level: i) processes, technologies that allow higher efficiency and circularity in processing of materials and manufacturing of products; ii) products, technologies that allow tracking and tracing of products and components, value chain optimisation, development of products as a service, increase reuse, repair, or refurbishment; iii) platforms, technologies that connect consumers and producers, allow development of services and dematerialisation.

3.1.1 The Milan experience

The Milan pilot in REFLOW focuses on food by tracking its flows across the city, specifically looking at the flows going through the city’s main food wholesale Market, SoGeMi, and the city’s 23 covered markets. To transition their urban food system towards becoming circular, the pilot project sets out to focus on specific food flows to test new food prototypes, support existing projects that transform food waste into new products, and enable initiatives that focus on reducing food waste at the wholesale and market stage. With SoGeMi as a key player in the Milan pilot, there is a strong emphasis on building solid business cases. This focus is reflected in the pilot solutions developed which push forward a local sustainable food system in Milan through circular food innovations.

3.1.2 Developing digital solutions to help citizens understand material flows to foster circular economy initiatives

The Milan pilot applied various solutions to rethink the current economy and reconfigure the urban metabolism towards a more sustainable urban food system. Particularly, Milan’s city pilot objectives were: i) *reducing waste upstream by*

⁴ ECERA, European Circular Economy Research Alliance (2020). *Digital circular economy as a cornerstone of a sustainable European industry transformation*.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

rethinking freight logistic based on intelligent tracking mechanism; ii) through donations recover what would be thrown away and is still edible; and iii) encourage the reuse-recycling of materials by certifying the circularity of processes.

The three different solutions developed occur in different ways to the objectives mentioned above. These solutions are:

1. **Food market 4.0 dashboard;**
2. **Foody zero waste - BOTTO;**
3. **Milano Prima Seconda.**

The **food market 4.0 dashboard** is an integrated system of both hardware and software solutions aiming to prevent food waste. The system allows for the tracking, management, data analysis and servitization of food flows in the covered markets.

BOTTO is an automated communication system for surplus fruit and vegetable products made available by wholesalers operating within **SO.GE.MI** to selected stakeholders, such as **RECUP**. **RECUP** is an NGO that operates in the city’s markets to combat food waste and social exclusion. Particularly, they recover the food before it is thrown away, divide it between edible and non-edible, and redistribute it to anyone who wants to take it. More specifically, **BOTTO** incorporates signal and tracking to facilitate the reallocation of surplus/unwanted food between fruit and vegetable wholesalers.

Lastly, **Milano Prima Seconda** is a distributed system of mapping, collection and exchange of waste materials as a starting point for different, higher value products produced through upcycling. The system supports organizations that claim to have a closed circular loop, but do not have the technical tools to track and trace which can prove this circularity.

For all three solutions it is evident that the **tracing** of the **material flows** is the starting condition. Moreover, tracing material flows should be done through simple systems that facilitate and do not complicate the processes. In this regard, **digital technology** should be the drivers of this change. Another point in common among these three solutions is the importance of the **co-creation** and **co-design** phases directly with the future users: these include the Municipality, wholesale market operators, retailers, logistics companies, active citizenship organizations, and citizens.

3.2 Recommendation 2

For a long time, cities have been growing in a way that necessitates long-distance commuting and traffic and air pollution. Cities have developed according to the citizen's need for mobility (physical ability to reach destinations) instead of their need for accessibility, the ability to gain access to services, goods and activities at destinations. Consequently, urban design has become car-focused, rather than addressing reasons for travel. It is in response to this, that the “15-minute city” concept has gained public attention, fostering increasing efforts towards the strengthening of the neighborhood scale.

When an urban area achieves the *15-minute city* goal⁵, becomes socio-economically equitable, and the convenient location of services, accessible by multiple modes, saves time and improves quality of life, and therefore more sustainable.

“The 15-minute city represents the possibility of a decentralized city. [...] At its heart is the concept of mixing urban social functions to create a vibrant vicinity⁶.”

Carlos Moreno

3.2.1 The Amsterdam experience

The **Amsterdam pilot in REFLOW** focuses on **textiles** used by its citizens, the way these textiles are discarded and reused, and how textiles as resources can be brought back into the city’s material flow. Overall, the Amsterdam pilot works towards achieving the desired long-lasting impact of transforming the textile stream from linear to circular. To facilitate the shift towards more circular textile material streams in the region, the Amsterdam pilot is implementing an overarching strategy consisting of two complementary scenarios, a short-term citizen scenario and a long-term industrial scenario. A core focal point in the Amsterdam pilot focuses on behavioral change starting with its citizens. Thus, the pilot team places a large emphasis on this within the development of their solutions. The short-term citizen scenario aims to achieve impact through behavioral change by empowering its citizens to become changemakers across two key goals:

1. to discard fewer textiles by extending textile lifecycles through reuse, repair, revaluing, and reducing;
2. to increase the collection of home textile waste by informing and engaging citizens to discard correctly.

The long-term industrial scenario is a corresponding continuation of the citizen scenario. Feeding into this long-term scenario, the support of more diverse strategies for the collection of textiles in the pilot project can aid the provision of feedstock for recycling industries, increase the demand for recycled textile, and support the supply of newly produced products out of recycled resources for other stakeholders.

3.2.2 Creation of neighborhood hotspots in line with the 15 minutes framework, on circularity of different material flows

The **swapshop** is a place where citizens can bring in their clothing and receive a “*swap*” voucher entitling them to an exchange of what is in the swapshop’s stock. Clothing in the store can only be purchased with a “*swap*” voucher. Clothing that goes into the swapshop is sorted, cleaned and repaired if needed, through which an overhead is paid as a service fee by the swapshops’s participants. The swapshop also incorporates a social aspect into its solution through the inclusion of people who are at distance from the job market.

Strikingly, the problem of the disposal of textiles was exacerbated by the Covid-19 pandemic. People at home were cleaning up more and more of their houses and filling the textile bins. In addition to that, due to the national safety restrictions, borders across nations were closed, and therefore the Municipality of Amsterdam decided to bring all the

⁵ Duany, A., & Steuteville, R. (2021, February). *Defining the 15-minute city*. Congress for the New Urbanism (CNU).

<https://www.cnu.org/publicsquare/2021/02/08/defining-15-minute-city>

⁶ https://www.ted.com/talks/carlos_moreno_the_15_minute_city/up-next#t-112749

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

collected textiles in a warehouse at Amsterdam-Noord. The loads of textile discarded there raised the attention of the citizens, journalists as well as the Municipality. This last, opened a call for action for circular solutions that could help to reduce the amount of clothes being discarded.

The winning solution of the swapshop was proposed by the *Startup in Residence* programme. Through the [Startup in Residence programme](#) the Municipality of Amsterdam invites startups to provide solutions for pre-defined urban and societal issues. Subsequently, a business plan was developed. Initially, the swapshop activities were run on a voluntary basis. In this regard, a training programme addressing unemployed people was established. Nowadays, the swapshop’s activities are run by paid workers as well as by volunteers.

Interestingly, *the Startup in Residence* programme is a young organization, which also has contact with students. This, from a circular economy perspective, is a strength because it permits the inclusion of students and youngsters, generally characterized by a lower spending capacity, in circular economy solutions.

Since the experimentation started, 8.000 swapped has been counted already. *Startup in Residence* programme aims to **create a network of swap shops in Amsterdam**, increasing the number of locations within The Municipality, but also beyond the city borders.

3.3 Recommendation 3

By recognizing designers’ responsibility, over the years, environmental philosophies have evolved from green design to **design for sustainability** and, more recently, **design for circularity** or **circular design**⁷. These approaches mean applying circular economy principles at the design stage of everything. It is a practice that embraces systems thinking to address some of the biggest interconnected challenges we are facing today. A future where products, services and systems are designed with the bigger picture in mind. A future where designers zoom in on user needs, while zooming out to consider the system in which they are creating, **including ease of maintenance and repair**.

The evolution of *circular design* has broadened its theoretical and practical scope over the years. While the first approaches were focusing predominantly on the technical side, the preceding ones have recognised the **crucial importance of the role of users**, the resilience of communities, and more generally of the various actors and dynamics of socio-technical systems⁸. Recent approaches to circular design require designers to be equipped with a different set of expertise such as techniques to gather insights from users, new ways of satisfying customers and techniques to **co-design** with all stakeholders.

3.3.1 The Vejle experience

The **Vejle pilot in REFLOW** focuses on **plastics** through gaining insights into urban plastic consumption and to increase the circularity of the city’s plastic value chains. The pilot project in Vejle dives into four micro-scale test sites in the Western neighborhood of the city – Vestbyen where the pilot project runs targeted experimentations, workshops, and

⁷ Moreno, M., De los Rios, C., Rowe, Z., & Charnley, F. (2016). A Conceptual Framework for Circular Design. *Sustainability*, 8(9), 937. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su8090937>

⁸ Ibid.

engagement sessions to identify and showcase solutions for increased plastic reuse, recovery, and reduction. These test sites include a retail store in the supermarket chain REMA 1000, the public housing block Den Gamle Gård, the public elderly home Sofiegården, and the innovation-hub Spinderihallerne. The Vejle pilot places a large emphasis on its citizens as changemakers towards reaching the Vejle pilot’s long-term goal of circular plastics. As such, this citizen focus is evident in the solutions that have been developed by Vejle pilot which seek to activate a citizen movement through empowering them to become informed and active in changemaking.

3.3.2 Mobilization of innovators capable of including citizens in experimenting with new circular solutions

The **new sorting solution** was applied at the apartment building *Den Gamle Gård*. This solution entails a new integrated way to dispose of plastic material directly in their kitchen. Through the **new sorting solution**, by removing the plastic out of the residual waste, the sorting rate will improve. Moreover, residents will be made more aware of waste and that it is possible to make new products out of household plastic waste.

Initially, a series of interviews and observations were conducted with a sample of tenants at *Den Gamle Gård* in order to identify the main challenges and issues on sorting plastics that tenants were encountering. Drawing upon this initial investigation an initial vision was drafted. Subsequently, together with a broad range of actors, among them designers and Fab-Lab, as well as technical actors, a **co-creation** workshop has been carried out. Through this co-creation moment more detailed ideas and possible concepts to be prototyped were developed.

The extracted concepts were, then, evaluated by the tenants and one was selected to be further developed and prototyped. Consequently, the innovator/s that could help in making the prototype were selected. In this regard, Wild Studio for the creation of **flower pots** made out of recycled plastic was selected. [Wild Studio](#) is uniquely placed in terms of collaborations with a closed loop agenda. They link design and industry, the consumer and the contributor. Their closed loop concept enables municipalities, institutions as well as bigger companies to integrate their waste strategy with Wild Studio’s design concept.

It was also important to create a community feeling around this intervention. Accordingly, pilot city partners were able to organize an event last August 2021. During this event, the **new sorting solution** and the **flower pot** were presented and shown to the entire community.

Most importantly, the **new sorting solution** started from the beginning from a citizens, and tenants’ point of view and real need. In a second moment, innovators and designers were added in the process to make this solution possible. This method is now being tested and replicated in a new housing development in Vejle.

3.4 Recommendation 4

The circular economy proposes an economic framework, restorative and regenerative by intention and design, based on circular flows of products and materials. A **transition** towards a circular economy is already underway and an

understanding of the nature and the state of this *transition* is important for the creation of effective policies, **profitable business models** and a more rapid exploitation of circular solutions⁹.

However, *transition* results in a complex process that requires changes in all the societal subsystems and not only in the economic system. Accordingly, it has been defined as “*a fundamental change in the structure, culture and practices of a societal (sub)system that is the result of a co-evolution of economic, technological, institutional, cultural and ecological developments at different scale levels*”¹⁰.

3.4.1 The Berlin experience

The **Berlin pilot in REFLOW** focuses on **wastewater heat** recovery to guide the city towards climate-neutral heating. Wastewater heat is generated as a by-product of water used in industrial processes and the everyday life of citizen activities such as showering, dishwashing, and doing laundry. The wastewater produced as a result of these processes often still contains high amounts of thermal energy, but much of this wastewater heat potential is lost after it goes down the drain and ends up in the sewer system.

In order to better utilize this underutilized resource, the Berlin pilot seeks to map the potential of wastewater and waste heat for its efficient recovery, to be further matched with heat demands in the city. Increasing awareness about this underutilized energy source is an important part of succeeding in this quest, and the pilot project aims to increase the visibility of the recovery of wastewater and waste heat as an important resource to achieve circularity and to tackle the challenges associated with climate change. Strategically, the Berlin pilot has pinpointed their focus on ensuring that the marketable solution being developed – wastewater heat – is a proven robust and sustainable business model being established that will drive implementation across Berlin and in other municipalities.

3.4.2 Facilitate the transition towards a circular economy by proactively sourcing home owner and tenant input regarding energy consumption

Sourcing energy consumption data refers to approaching the cooperative or building owners in order to source intel about energy consumption of properties, thereby triggering interest in a more sustainable way of heating. Specifically, this solution would make tenants and home owners aware of circular heating options, and it also extends the network of the actors involved and the citizen community.

As a first step to employ this solution it is important to identify the right actors to approach. In this regard, pilot city partners focus on **cooperatives**, therefore engaging with tenants who are also shareholders of the building they are living in. Random tenants would not work effectively because tenants are mainly interested in what they are going to pay and generally not interested in long term investment.

⁹ Kevin van Langen, S., Vassillo, C., Ghisellini, P., Restaino, D., Passaro, R., & Ulgiati, S. (2021). Promoting circular economy transition: A study about perceptions and awareness by different stakeholders groups. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 316, 128166. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.128166

¹⁰ Grin, J., Rotmans, J., & Schot, J. (2010). *Transitions to sustainable development: new directions in the study of long term transformative change*. Routledge.

Representatives of the cooperatives and tenants were asked about their energy consumption in two different ways: i) printed flyers with a QR code which directly would link them to an online form where they were able to compile with the intel requested; ii) and directly by a phone call.

Importantly, experts by checking the compiled questionnaire were able to understand if the property was eligible or not for the implementation of a **wastewater heat system**. Subsequently, whether the building is eligible it is explained to them a clear **call for action**. While, for the ones who are not eligible for the implementation of a wastewater heat system a free energy consumption analysis is offered.

It is pivotal that the follow up of the compilation of the questionnaire is **reliable** and **includes a clear value add perspective**. Hence, there should be mentioned savings for the cooperative or property owners and a clear roadmap of what it is suggested to do next.

3.5 Recommendation 5

To enable a transition toward a circular economy it is necessary the contribution of a variety of stakeholders, from the private sector, startups and entrepreneurs and public. However, it is implied that the transition to a circular economy is dependent on how individuals and organizations learn to innovate and apply what they've learned in the real world.

The **education sector**, from primary school to postgraduate study, plays a vital role in ensuring students of all ages are equipped with the key skills and knowledge to apply circular thinking in their chosen careers. Accordingly, Pandey and Vedak¹¹ say: “*education is the key intervention for bringing change in knowledge, values, behaviors and lifestyles [...] required to achieve sustainable development*” (p. 3). Even though, this has received still little attention in the higher education, universities have progressively incorporated sustainability education in their curricula since the early 1990s¹².

3.5.1 The Cluj-Napoca context

The **Cluj-Napoca pilot in REFLOW** focuses on **energy** through improving the energy efficiency of public buildings and residential homes throughout the city. To work towards this goal, the pilot sets out the following objectives: to assess how the measures taken to date by the city have impacted the energy efficiency of selected buildings; to involve local stakeholders in implementing and furthering these measures; and to encourage different actors in the ecosystem to propose new ideas regarding renewable energy sources to be integrated into the city's strategy for a circular economy. Coinciding with these objectives, the pilot project seeks to educate its citizens on circular economy, its benefits, and possibilities.

¹¹ Pandey, N., & Vedak, V. (2009). Structural transformation of education for sustainable development. *International Journal Environmental Sustainable Development*. DOI: 10.1504/IJESD.2010.030063

¹² Kirchherr, J., & Piscicelli, L. (2019). Towards an education for the circular economy (ECE): Five teaching principles and a case study. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 150, 104406. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2019.104406>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

3.5.2 Building a future generation of circular citizens and professionals

The **Cluj-Napoca** pilot’s aim was to **raise awareness and empower youngsters and future professionals** on the topic of energy transition, sustainability and circularity. This process followed four main steps: **awareness, understanding, application** and **creation**.

In the first phase, it was necessary to **disseminate** Reflow in Cluj-Napoca and to make citizens and professionals aware of this opportunity and explain to them the necessity of this project. On these occasions, roundtables with several stakeholders, like city administrators, business, professors, researchers as well as teachers were attended. In addition to that, public events have taken place.

However, only hearing about this matter is usually not sufficient. Students, either from the technical high school, as well as from the university were **tested** in order to evaluate how much they knew about circular economy and related studies.

The third important step was **application**. This refers to the most important solution of Cluj-Napoca pilot, the **curriculum for MA level course on Circular Economy**, as well as the application of the **energy tree**, another pilot solution, through which everyone can gather information on circular economy in public spaces.

Last step of the process is to **put the theoretical knowledge into practice**. Students, from the high school as well as from university during their courses will be encouraged to create and implement an action plan, and work with projects related to the circular economy.

3.6 Recommendation 6

Following the principles of circular economy, initiatives in the same neighborhood, district or city, can use each other’s material resources, at low transportation costs. However, it is important to help different actors to build ties with each other. In this perspective, the notion of the **innovation ecosystem**, borrowed by business and technology fields from ecology, can help us to better understand how these civic networks function¹³. Ecosystems are more than an accumulation of actors: they are also made up by “enabling policies and regulations, accessibility of finance, informed human capital, supportive markets, energy, transport and communications infrastructure, a culture supportive of innovation and entrepreneurship, and networking assets, which together support productive relationships between different actors and other parts of the ecosystem.”¹⁴

Following the logic of natural and innovative ecosystems, recently has been conceived the term of **civic ecosystems**¹⁵ - similarly to natural or business ecosystems - “not only foster interactions but facilitate symbiotic relationships among the various initiatives launched within its environment” as well as “optimize the flow of talent and knowledge if they

¹³ Polyak, L., Bod, S., Brody, L., (2021): The power of civic ecosystems: How community spaces and their networks make our cities more cooperative, fair and resilient. Cooperative City Books, Vienna.

¹⁴ IDEA (International Development Innovation Alliance) <https://www.idiainnovation.org/ecosystem>

¹⁵ Polyak, L., Bod, S., Brody, L., (2021) *Op. cit.*

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

share a geographical proximity. By developing a certain collective intelligence, such ecosystems move “from a collection of elements to a more structured community.”¹⁶

3.6.1 The Paris experience

The **Paris pilot in REFLOW** focuses on **timber and wood** used in the event and temporary construction industry in the city. The pilot project sets out to quantify and qualify the waste material flows generated from events and temporary structures through the development of new models and digital tools to facilitate the reuse of wood materials and products and to accelerate the transition of these sectors towards circular models. Concretely, the pilot projects prototypes and tests digital tracking and scanning tools that leverage computational design techniques in their incubator, Driven Studio. Through the identification and quantification of these material flows, wood can be monitored and reintegrated back into manufacturing processes, ultimately extending the material’s life cycle. In addition to the track and trace of materials, facilitated through the pilot’s incubator, tools capable of generating databases of wood products to support the development of an agile digital marketplace will increase exchange between the event and temporary construction sectors. The development of robust business models around digital tracking tools is a key focus for the Paris pilot to support the emerging circular event industry, and as such it is reflected in the pilot solutions that have been focused on and developed.

3.6.2 Creating a network of practitioners to foster circular economy solutions

On an international scale, certificates are common ways to ensure sustainable production, but such international labels are often out of reach for smaller makers, operating on a local or even neighborhood level. [Ars Longa](#), a pilot city partner, developed [RE-Label](#). It provides both a more approachable certification that can be adapted to local needs and support for artisans aiming to become more circular in their production.

Re-Label offers a toolbox of tools and services to local makers to better valorise their work, reduce the generation of wood scraps, increase reuse of those scraps that are unavoidable, and increase sales. The improved valorisation is made possible by offering a certificate for the product, which shows the specificities and singularities of their creation.

In the creation of *Re-Label*, city partners, firstly, reached out to the existing communities of creatives and investigated their challenges in terms of circularity and circular design. Upon them, pilot city’s partners thought how they could improve the way creatives currently organize themselves and work. This network of existing creatives was then displayed in an interactive and open [map](#). *Re-Label* makes it possible to visualize the state of ecosystems in the different territories, and members are divided in four main categories:

1. Designers, architects, artisans, creators;
2. Manufacturing workshops, carpentry, ceramics, metal;
3. Suppliers, resources or storage space;
4. Partner structures, institutions, incubators.

¹⁶ Moore, James F. (1993) *Predators and Prey: A New Ecology of Competition*. Harvard Business Review.

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Re-Label offers local makers and workshops, using wood as their main material, a territorial community of stakeholders to share their sustainable practices. Makers, who wish to promote and evaluate their range of eco-responsible objects, can join the *RE-label* community in their territory to increase their network. Manufacturers can discover suitable partners to interchange wood scraps and support a circular use of material and waste reduction. The local community further functions as an inspiration for re-use practices in the area and invites makers to share their own practices.

The information includes origin, measurements, history, quality of the material, and time spent by the maker, and is gathered in the Re-Label certificate edited by an online generator. The document is dated and signed by the designer or the workshop manager to raise awareness for the consumer.

Conclusion

The deliverable “Circular Citizens and Capacity Building” aimed to give a complete and substantial understanding on the citizens’ role in the implementation of circular solutions in the six pilot cities. Importantly, in the framework of REFLOW the innovative solutions tested in the six pilot cities focused on different materials: food, textiles, plastic, energy, waste-water heat, and wood.

Throughout the project a broad variety of stakeholders were engaged in the different pilot solutions: tenants, cooperatives, NGOs, public and private companies, entrepreneurs, social enterprises, designers, professors and students, and youngsters. All of which with different and relevant roles.

An addition of the deliverable are the recommendations, also collected in the “Circular Citizens Handbook”. These recommendations derived from the pilot experiences in developing their own strategies end the engagement of the citizens. The recommendations targeted policy makers and municipalities for citizen’s participation in the circular economy transition. These were drawn by considering the different dimensions of REFLOW: materials flows and tracking of data, technology and platforms, urban dimension, and network of social innovators and entrepreneurs.

Each recommendation focuses on different aspects: digital technologies, 15-minutes framework, circular design and design for sustainability, strategies in support of the circular transition, creation of education and university curricula, and the setting up of a civic ecosystem.

The recommendations emerging from the Reflow experience are:

1. Developing digital solutions to help citizens understand material flows to foster circular economy initiatives: Digital technologies are an enabler for the upscaling of the circular economy as they allow the creation and processing of data and information required for circular business models and the complex demands of circular supply chains.
2. Creation of neighborhood hotspots in line with the 15 minutes framework, on circularity of different material flows: as when an urban area achieves the 15-minute city goal, becomes socio-economically equitable, and the convenient location of services, accessible by multiple modes, saves time and improves quality of life, and therefore more sustainable.
3. Mobilization of innovators capable of including citizens in experimenting with new circular solutions: By recognizing designers’ responsibility, over the years, environmental philosophies have evolved from green design to design for sustainability and, more recently, design for circularity or circular design.
4. Facilitate the transition towards a circular economy by proactively sourcing home owner and tenant input regarding energy consumption: “a fundamental change in the structure, culture and practices of a societal (sub)system that is the result of a co-evolution of economic, technological, institutional, cultural and ecological developments at different scale levels
5. Building a future generation of circular citizens and professionals: The education sector, from primary school to postgraduate study, plays a vital role in ensuring students of all ages are equipped with the key skills and knowledge to apply circular thinking in their chosen careers.
6. Creating a network of practitioners to foster circular economy solutions: Ecosystems are more than an accumulation of actors: they are also made up by “enabling policies and regulations, accessibility of finance,

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informed human capital, supportive markets, energy, transport and communications infrastructure, a culture supportive of innovation and entrepreneurship, and networking assets, which together support productive relationships between different actors and other parts of the ecosystem.”

Lastly, the cases that we reported were different from each other, with their own technicalities and challenges to overcome. Therefore, it is not expected that these solutions could be replicated in the same manner elsewhere. Our aim is that REFLOW could work as an inspiration for other European municipalities, policy makers and urban practitioners that desire to move towards a more inclusive urban circular metabolism.